

THE EFFECT OF PREVIOUS VIRAL HEPATITIS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PANCREATIC PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN

A.V. Muratkhodzhaeva

DSc, Professor, Head of the Department of Faculty Pediatrics, Tashkent State Medical University

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Abstract. *The article discusses the problem of the formation of functional and chronic inflammatory processes in the pancreas after viral hepatitis. It has been established that after viral hepatitis A, changes in the pancreas often manifest as functional disorders, despite concomitant damage to the biliary tract in the form of dyskinesia. After viral hepatitis B, changes in the pancreas are characterized by the formation of a chronic inflammatory process.*

Keywords: *viral hepatitis, chronic pancreatitis, biliary tract dyskinesia, gallbladder, bilirubin.*

Abstract. It has been established that chronic pancreatitis is almost always the outcome of acute pancreatitis. The direct transition from the acute form to the chronic form is relatively rare. Many aspects of the etiology of chronic pancreatitis coincide with the etiology of acute pancreatitis. The etiology of chronic pancreatitis is determined by the role of biliary tract pathology and the possibility of its development after cholecystectomy. Prolonged duodenal ulcer disease and chronic gastritis also contribute to the development of the disease. There is little information about the significance of the infectious factor in the etiology of chronic pancreatitis. Certain types of clinical infections and some exanthematous diseases (mumps) are considered to be etiological factors in the development of chronic pancreatitis. Viral hepatitis is one of the main causes of chronic hepatitis. With viral hepatitis, damage to the pancreas tends to become chronic [1].

In acute infectious diseases, the causative agents of which show tropism for the pancreas, its damage is observed, sometimes with the development of acute pancreatitis and subsequent transformation into a chronic form. Clinical manifestations of pancreatic damage can take the form of functional disorders and the formation of a chronic inflammatory process. Pancreatopathy syndrome in some infectious diseases can be clearly defined, while in others it is not clearly pronounced, and this is the complexity of the clinical analysis of possible pancreatic damage in infectious diseases in children. In such cases, after the elimination of the manifestations of acute infectious disease without appropriate observation and treatment, the development of chronic pancreatic pathology is possible [2].

Objective: to study the effect of previous viral hepatitis on the development of pancreatic pathology in children.

Materials and methods. We observed 65 children aged 6 to 14 years with a history of viral hepatitis, of whom 45 had viral hepatitis A and 20 had viral hepatitis B. None of them had pancreatic damage during the acute phase of the disease. The duration of hepatitis was 8 months to 1.5 years. All patients complained of pain syndrome, but in 35 children with localization not corresponding to liver damage, dyspeptic syndrome in this group of children was characterized by nausea, decreased appetite, selective appetite, unstable stool with changes in feces (fatty, shiny,

sometimes paste-like). A large amount of neutral fat was detected in the coprogram. This group of children had a history of viral hepatitis B (90%) and hepatitis A (38%) [3].

For diagnostic purposes, biochemical blood tests were performed to characterize the functional state of the liver, determine the levels of ALT, AST, alkaline phosphatase, and bilirubin, as well as amylase and lipase in the blood and urine. The state of the intestinal microbiota was studied by conducting a bacteriological analysis of the intestinal microflora. [4]. All patients underwent ultrasound examination of the liver (size and condition of the parenchyma), gallbladder (shape, size, condition of the walls, contents), and pancreas (size, parenchyma, condition of the pancreatic duct) [5].

The studies revealed that out of 35 children with clinical symptoms indicating possible involvement of the pancreas in the pathological process, ultrasound examination showed a slight increase in the size of the pancreas without changes in its echogenicity (25 children). Of the total number of children in this group, ultrasound examination of the liver revealed an anomaly in the development of the bile ducts in 9 patients, accounting for 36%. Of these, 4 children had an S-shaped bend in the gallbladder, 3 children had a constriction in the body, and 2 patients had a bend in the neck of the gallbladder. During follow-up at 3 and 6 months, no changes in the pancreas were detected on ultrasound, and biochemical blood and urine tests during follow-up showed no pathological abnormalities. The changes observed were assessed as functional disorders of the pancreas. These children were monitored by a gastroenterologist, their diet was adjusted, and enzyme preparations were prescribed for replacement therapy. Particular attention was paid to the diet of this group of children, with the exclusion of fatty and fried foods [6].

In 10 children who had viral hepatitis B, ultrasound examination revealed an enlarged pancreas with reduced echogenicity, and biochemical blood tests showed increased amylase activity in 2 children and elevated amylasemia in 4 children. All children had a history of viral hepatitis B. The data obtained allowed a diagnosis of pancreatitis to be made. Clinical observation and examination showed that the chronic course of pancreatitis manifested itself primarily in exocrine insufficiency of the pancreas. The course of exocrine pancreatic insufficiency was reflected in clinical and laboratory manifestations. Clinical manifestations were characterized by the appearance of abdominal pain, different from typical pancreatic pain attacks, without particular severity. In 30% of cases, children in this group experienced weight loss and severe flatulence. Four patients had prolonged jaundice of moderate severity. Pain syndrome was particularly pronounced in the right hypochondrium [7].

It should be noted that in 2% of cases of chronic pancreatitis with exocrine insufficiency, constant abdominal pain was observed. Abdominal pain was localized in the abdomen on the right and left slightly above the navel, sometimes in the left hypochondrium. The pain was not girdle-like in nature, but radiation to the lower back and left shoulder was noted. Usually, the intensification of abdominal pain was associated with food intake (heavy meals, consumption of fatty, cold, and hot foods) [8].

Dyspeptic symptoms manifested as heaviness and bloating in the abdomen, a sharp decrease in appetite, and moderate diarrhea [9]. Observations during diet therapy and the administration of enzymes, antispasmodics, and H₂ histamine receptor blockers showed an improvement in the patients' condition and normalization of blood and urine biochemical parameters. In order to restore the biological environment in the clinic and improve its physiological function, the prebiotic Hilak-forte was prescribed.

CREON-10000 was prescribed for enzyme therapy. Duspatalin was prescribed as an antispasmodic to relieve pancreatic pain. However, an ultrasound examination revealed a decrease in pancreatic size while the echogenicity of the glandular parenchyma remained low. Particular attention was paid to diet, excluding fatty, fried, and spicy foods. Probiotics, which have positive effects on physiological and metabolic functions when administered naturally, were used to normalize the intestinal microbiota [10].

Results. Studies have shown that children who have had viral hepatitis may develop pancreatic damage. Signs of pancreatic damage are often not diagnosed during the acute phase of the disease, but may become apparent during convalescence. In viral hepatitis B, the frequency of involvement of the pancreas in the pathological process is significantly higher than in viral hepatitis A. Pancreatic damage can be functional, which is more common in children who have had viral hepatitis A, or organic, with the formation of an inflammatory process, which is more common in children who have had viral hepatitis B.

Conclusion. Thus, analysis of the literature and specific research results has shown that viral hepatitis in children can lead to pancreatic damage in the form of functional disorders and organic changes with the development of an inflammatory process. Signs of pancreatic damage can be diagnosed not only in the acute phase, but also during convalescence. A history of viral hepatitis B contributes to pancreatic damage in children with greater frequency. Observations indicate the need for thorough medical examinations of children who have had viral hepatitis, with monitoring of not only the liver but also other digestive organs.

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